

Studies in the Cyclohexane Series. Part XVIII. Ring Opening of the Anhydride of 1-Carboxy 3, 4-dimethyl- cyclohexane-1-acetic acid during Friedel-Crafts reaction and Synthesis of 2, 3-dimethyl-8, 9-benzo and Substituted 8, 9- benzospiro (5, 5) undecanes

R. K. GAUTAM and G. S. SAHARIA

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007.

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The ring opening of the anhydride of 1-carboxy 3, 4 dimethyl-cyclohexane-1-acetic acid, m.p. 160° has been studied by converting the anhydride into the half-ester, its acid chloride and finally condensing it with benzene. The keto-ester so obtained on hydrolysis gave the keto-acid which was identical with the one obtained by the condensation of the anhydride with benzene under Friedel-Crafts reaction conditions.

This anhydride was later condensed with toluene and isomeric xylenes to give the corresponding $\alpha\alpha$ -(3', 4'-dimethylcyclohexane)- β -aroylpropionic acids. All the keto-acids on catalytic reduction furnished $\alpha\alpha$ -(3', 4'-dimethylcyclohexane)- γ -aryl-n-butyric acids which on cyclisation with PPA followed by Clemmensen reduction yielded 2, 3-dimethyl-8, 9-benzo and substituted 8, 9-benzospiro (5, 5) undecanes.

In order to determine the mode of opening of the anhydride ring during Friedel-Crafts reaction and confirm the earlier findings¹, the anhydride of 1-carboxy 3, 4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid², m.p. 160° was converted into its half ester. This half ester was later converted into its acid chloride and subsequently subjected to Friedel-Crafts reaction with benzene. The keto-ester so obtained on hydrolysis furnished the keto-acid of the type IV (X=O) having m. p. identical with the one obtained by the Friedel-Crafts reaction of the anhydride with benzene and the mixed m.ps. of the two remained undepressed. Based on these reactions, the half ester has been assigned the structure I (X=H) and not of the type II as contended by some workers.³

Further theoretical reasoning also renders support to the structure assigned; of the two groups —COOH and —CH₂COOH present at C-1 in the molecules of the parent acid, the group —CH₂COOH being bulkier would occupy the equatorial position. The difference of free energy between the equatorial and axial —COOH and —COOCH₃ groups has been estimated to be 1.7 and 1.0 K cal/mole⁴ respectively. On the basis of this free energy data IIIa would be stabler as compared to IIIb by 0.7 K cal/mole and therefore, the anhydride ring on opening would give the former.

III
a — R = CH₃; R₁ = H
b — R = H; R₁ = CH₃

Friedel-Crafts condensation of the anhydrides of 1-carboxy 4-, 3- and 2-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acids with aromatic hydrocarbons has been reported⁵. With a view to study the bearing of disubstitution in the cyclohexane moiety on the analogous reaction and to compare this with unsubstituted and monosubstituted cyclohexane analogues, the condensation of the anhydride of 1-carboxy 3, 4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid, m.p. 160° with benzene, toluene and isomeric xylenes has been carried out. In all these cases only one keto-acid, $\alpha\alpha$ -(3', 4'-dimethylcyclohexane)- β -aroylpropionic acid^{5,6,7} of the type IV (X=O) was obtained; the structures of these were confirmed by the formation of pyrylium salts and oxidation with sodium hypobromite to the known aromatic acids. These keto-acids were characterised by the formation of their 2, 4-DNPs, equivalent weight and I. R. spectral data (1690 cm⁻¹ (ketone) and 1710 cm⁻¹ carboxylic group).

During this condensation a small amount of a neutral product was always encountered which added up bromine and on the basis of elemental analysis and IR spectral data (1875 cm⁻¹ correspon-

ding to $\beta\gamma$ -unsaturated- γ -lactone) it has been assigned the lactonic structure^{5,6,8}. The yield of the neutral product was greater in the case of isomeric xylenes than with benzene and toluene⁵ and these were found to be dependent on temperature being minimum at 0-5°.

$\alpha\alpha$ -(3', 4'-Dimethylcyclohexane)- β -benzoylpropionic acid on Clemmensen reduction gave $\alpha\alpha$ -(3', 4'-dimethylcyclohexane)- γ -phenyl-*n*-butyric acid along with a small quantity of a neutral product. When this method of reduction was applied to the other keto-acids, the yields of the reduced acids diminished considerably and those of the neutral product increased to ~85%.

This difference in the reactivity of keto-acids towards Clemmensen reduction could be attributed to the presence of an additional methyl group in the cyclohexane moiety which may partly be responsible for the formation of the neutral product in larger amounts. This neutral product on the basis of analytical and I. R. spectral data (1775 cm^{-1} ; lactonic group) has been assigned a lactonic structure^{5,6,8}.

These keto-acids, however, could be reduced with palladium-charcoal (10%) under pressure to the corresponding butyric acids (IV; X=H₂) in high yields (60-70%) and were characterised by elemental analysis, equivalent weight and I. R. spectral data (1710 cm^{-1}).

Our attempts to reduce the above keto-acids by modified Wolf-Kishner method⁹ also did not meet with success as here again neutral products were obtained (~90%); on the basis of elemental analysis and I.R. spectral data (1670 : γ C=O; 3175 : γ N-H and 1610 cm^{-1} : γ C=N) these neutral products have been found to be present in the dimeric form of the monomer, a δ -lactam⁵.

Cyclisation of the reduced acids with freshly prepared PPA⁶ furnished the spiro-ketones of the type V (Y=O) characterised through their 2, 4 DNPs and I.R. peaks (1685 cm^{-1} : γ C=O). Their subsequent reduction by modified Clemmensen method furnished the corresponding spiro-hydrocarbons of the type V (Y=H₂).

Experimental

1-Carbomethoxy 3, 4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid

A solution of the anhydride of 1-carboxy 3, 4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid, m.p. 160° (2 g) in

absolute methanol (25 ml) was heated under reflux on a water bath (12 hrs). Excess of methanol was removed under vacuum, the residue taken up in ether, the ethereal solution washed with aqueous sodium carbonate (5%; 4 x 30 ml) and the alkaline solution on acidification with dil. hydrochloric acid deposited an oil. This on distillation instead of the half ester gave the anhydride b.p. 164°/5 mm and, therefore, for subsequent work the undistilled product was employed. (Found: equiv., 227.2. C₁₂H₂₀O₄ requires 228.0—monobasic). I.R. γ_{max}^{KBr} 1735 cm^{-1} (ester) and 1710 cm^{-1} (carboxylic group).

Acid chloride of 1-carbomethoxy 3, 4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid

1-Carbomethoxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid (1.8 g; 0.005 mole) and thionyl chloride (5 ml) were refluxed on a water bath (4 hrs). Excess of thionyl chloride was removed at water pump and the residue on distillation gave the acid chloride of 1-carbomethoxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid, b.p. 142°/11 mm, n_D^{20} 1.5216. (Yield: 81.5%). (Found: C, 56.6; H, 7.4; Cl, 14.1. C₁₂H₁₉O₃Cl requires C, 56.8; H, 7.7; Cl, 14.3%). IR γ_{max}^{KBr} 1735 cm^{-1} (ester) and 1795 cm^{-1} (acid chloride).

Methyl $\alpha\alpha$ -(3',4'-dimethylcyclohexane)- β -benzoylpropionate

A solution of the above acid chloride (1.25 g; 0.005 mole) in dry benzene was cooled in an ice-salt bath (0-5°) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.7 g; 0.005 mole) added in small lots with shaking and cooling. The contents were kept in an ice-salt bath for 2 hours and left overnight at room temperature. The reaction mixture was heated in an oil bath at 60-70° (2 hours), and the complex decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid; on working up in the usual manner, methyl $\alpha\alpha$ -(3',4'-dimethylcyclohexane)- β -benzoylpropionate distilled at 156°/8 mm. n_D^{20} 1.5137. (Yield: 85.4%). (Found: C, 74.8; H, 8.2. C₁₈H₂₄O₃ requires C, 75.0; H, 8.3% I.R. γ_{max}^{KBr} : 1735 cm^{-1} (ester) and 1690 cm^{-1} (ketone).

$\alpha\alpha$ -(3',4'-Dimethylcyclohexane)- β -benzoylpropionic acid

The above ester (1.0 g) was refluxed with aqueous sodium hydroxide (10%; 20 ml) (2 hours), the alkaline solution cooled, and acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid. The deposited solid on crystallisation from benzene-petrol (60-80) gave $\alpha\alpha$ -(3',4'-dimethylcyclohexane)- β -benzoylpropionic acid, m.p. 114°. (Yield: 71.3%).

(Found: C, 74.4; H, 7.8. equiv., 273.5. C₁₇H₂₂O₃ requires C, 74.5; H, 8.0%; equiv., 274.0 monobasic).

Mixed m.p. of the above with the keto-acid obtained by the condensation of the anhydride of 1-carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid,

m.p. 160° with benzene in the ratio (1 : 1) showed no depression.

The anhydride of 1-carboxy 3,4-dimethylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid m.p. 160°, obtained by refluxing it with acetic anhydride had b.p. 155/4 mm. n_D^{25} 1.5314. (Yield : 90.0%).

(Found : C, 67.3 ; H, 8.0. $C_{11}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 67.6 ; H, 8.2%).

Synthesis of 2,3-dimethyl-8,9-benzo and substituted 8,9-benzospiro (5,5) undecanes

$\alpha\alpha$ -(3',4'-Dimethylcyclohexane)- β -aroylpropionic acids

To the cooled solution (0.5) of the anhydride (3.92 g ; 0.02 mole) in dry hydrocarbon (25 ml) was added powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (5.34 g ; 0.04 mole) in small lots during shaking. The reaction mixture was kept in an ice-salt bath for 2-3 hours, shaken vigorously at intervals, left at room temperature for 24 hours and then heated in an oil bath (60-70°) for 2 hours. The complex was decomposed with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid, and on working up in the normal manner the above titled acids on crystallisation from benzene-pet. ether (60-80°) gave $\alpha\alpha$ -(3',4'-dimethyl cyclohexane)- β -aroylpropionic acids which are entered in Table 1.

$\alpha\alpha$ -(3', 4'-Dimethylcyclohexane)- γ -aryl-*n*-butyric acids

A solution of $\alpha\alpha$ -(3', 4'-dimethylcyclohexane- β -aroylpropionic acids (3.0 g) in alcohol (25 ml) containing Pd/C (200 mg ; 10%) was treated with hydrogen (8 hrs) in a Paar apparatus at 35-40° under 35-40 lb/psi. The solution was filtered, the filtrate diluted with water, extracted with ether and the ethereal solution shaken with aqueous sodium carbonate (5% ; 4 x 50 ml). The alkaline extract on acidification deposited an oil which was taken up in ether, the ethereal solution dried (anhydrous $MgSO_4$) and the solvent removed. The residue depending upon its state was purified by crystallisation from benzene-petrol (60-80°) or by vacuum distillation and these reduced acids are recorded in Table 2.

2, 3-Dimethyl-8, 9-benzo and substituted 8, 9-benzo-10-keto-spiro (5,5) undecanes

Each of the above butyric acid (1.5 g) after dissolving in polyphosphoric acid (prepared from phosphorus pentoxide, 15 g and orthophosphoric acid, 10 ml) was heated in an oil bath maintained at 180-90° with occasional shaking (2 hrs). The contents were poured over crushed ice (300 g) during stirring, extracted with ether, the ethereal solution

TABLE 1

 $\alpha\alpha$ -(3', 4'-DIMETHYLCYCLOHEXANE)- β -AROYLPROPIONIC ACIDS

Aroyl	M.P. °C	Yield %	Eq. wt. (monobasic)	Mol. Formula	Analysis				2, 4-DNP °C
					Found %		Requires %		
					C	H	C	H	
1. Benzoyl	114	96.1	273.5	$C_{11}H_{16}O_3$	74.4	7.8	74.5	8.0	220
2. 4-Methylbenzoyl	156.7	83.9	285.8	$C_{10}H_{14}O_3$	74.9	8.2	75.0	8.3	215
3. 3, 4-Dimethylbenzoyl	107	77.7	301.6	$C_{10}H_{16}O_3$	75.5	8.7	75.5	8.6	177-8
4. 2, 4-Dimethylbenzoyl	121	71.2	301.5	"	75.4	8.7	"	"	175
5. 2, 5-Dimethylbenzoyl	127	67.9	301.8	"	75.3	8.6	"	"	218

$\alpha\alpha$ -(3',4'-Dimethylcyclohexane)- γ -phenyl-*n*-butyric acid

$\alpha\alpha$ -(3', 4'-Dimethylcyclohexane)- β -benzoylpropionic acid (4.0 g) was reduced by modified Clemmensen method by refluxing the contents on a sand bath for 60 hrs. On working up the reaction product in the usual manner, $\alpha\alpha$ -(3',4'-dimethylcyclohexane)- γ -phenyl-*n*-butyric acid distilled at 135-6°/2-3 mm. n_D^{25} 1.5312. (Yield : 71.1%).

(Found : C, 78.5 ; H, 9.2 ; equiv., 259.7. $C_{17}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 78.5 ; H, 9.2% ; 260.0-monobasic).

Other keto-acids on reduction by Clemmensen method gave the reduced acid in extremely poor yields but these were, however, obtained in satisfactory yields by catalytic reduction.

first washed with aqueous sodium hydroxide (5%) and then with water. The ethereal solution was dried (anhydrous $MgSO_4$), ether recovered and the residue on distillation gave 2, 3-dimethyl-8, 9-benzo and substituted 8, 9-benzo-10-keto-spiro (5,5) undecanes which are given in Table 3.

2, 3-Dimethyl-8, 9-benzo and substituted 8, 9-benzospiro (5, 5) undecanes

The spiro-ketone (0.8 g) was refluxed with amalgamated zinc (40 g), toluene (5 ml) glacial acetic acid (2 ml) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (60 ml) for 65-70 hrs. The reaction product on working up in the normal manner gave 2, 3-dimethyl-8, 9-benzo and substituted 8, 9-benzospiro (5,5) undecanes (Table 4).

TABLE 2

 $\alpha\alpha$ -(3', 4'-DIMETHYLCYCLOHEXANE)- γ -ARYL-N-BUTYRIC ACIDS

Aryl	M.P./b.p. °C	Yield %	Eq. wt. (monobasic)	Mol. formula	Analysis			
					Found %		Requires %	
					C	H	C	H
1. Methylphenyl*	180	70.0	273.8	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₂	78.6	9.8	78.8	9.5
2. 3, 4-Dimethylphenyl	191-2/3 mm	73.4	287.5	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ O ₂	79.0	9.6	79.2	9.7
3. 2, 4-Dimethylphenyl	165	66.4	287.7	"	79.1	9.6	"	"
4. 2, 5-Dimethylphenyl	118	70.0	287.5	"	79.0	9.6	"	"

* Lactone of $\alpha\alpha$ -(3', 4'-dimethylcyclohexane)- γ -hydroxy- γ -4-methylphenyl-n-butyric acid obtained during the Clemmensen reduction had m. p, 254-6°.

(Found : C, 79.2 ; H, 8.7. C₁₈H₂₀O₂ requires C, 79.4 ; H, 8.8%).

IR γ Nujol max 1775 cm⁻¹ (lactone).

TABLE 3

2, 3-DIMETHYL-8, 9-BENZO AND SUBSTITUTED 8, 9-BENZO-10-KETO-SPIRO (5, 5) UNDECANES

Substituent in the benzene ring	b.p. °C	Yield %	Ref. index	Mol. formula	Analysis				2, 4 DNP °C
					Found %		Requires %		
					C	H	C	H	
1. R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =R ₄ =H	132/4 mm	71.6	n _D ^{24.5} 1.4987	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ O	84.2	9.0	84.3	9.2	195-6
2. R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =H ; R ₄ =CH ₃	165-6/9 mm	64.2	n _D ^{24.5} 1.4996	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O	84.3	9.1	84.4	9.4	147
3. R ₁ =R ₄ =H ; R ₂ =R ₃ =CH ₃	176/5 mm	64.0	n _D ²⁴ 1.5078	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O	84.2	9.7	84.4	9.8	171
4. R ₁ =R ₂ =H ; R ₃ =R ₄ =CH ₃	181/7 mm	78.2	n _D ^{24.5} 1.5089	"	84.3	9.5	"	"	176
5. R ₂ =R ₃ =H ; R ₁ =R ₄ =CH ₃	169/2 mm	67.6	n _D ^{24.5} 1.5050	"	84.2	9.5	"	"	212

TABLE 4

2, 3-DIMETHYL-8, 9-BENZO AND SUBSTITUTED 8, 9-BENZO-SPIRO (5, 5) UNDECANES

Substituent in the benzene ring	b.p. °C	Yield %	Ref. index	Mol. formula	Analysis			
					Found %		Requires %	
					C	H	C	H
1. R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =R ₄ =H	95-6/2 mm	53.1	n _D ^{28.5} 1.4875	C ₁₇ H ₂₄	89.4	10.3	89.5	10.5
2. R ₁ =R ₂ =R ₃ =H ; R ₄ =CH ₃	162/10 mm	66.1	n _D ²⁹ 1.5035	C ₁₈ H ₂₆	89.1	10.6	89.3	10.7
3. R ₁ =R ₄ =H ; R ₂ =R ₃ =CH ₃	165/4 mm	46.0	n _D ²⁴ 1.5350	C ₁₈ H ₂₆	89.0	10.7	89.1	10.9
4. R ₁ =R ₂ =H ; R ₃ =R ₄ =CH ₃	185/8 mm	60.2	n _D ²⁸ 1.5401	"	89.0	10.8	"	"
5. R ₃ =R ₄ =H ; R ₁ =R ₂ =CH ₃	179/3 mm	60.0	n _D ²² 1.5521	"	89.1	10.7	"	"

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